

CULTURAL INFLUENCE ON DRUG ABUSE: A STUDY OF TOBACCO ABUSE AMONG IBIBIO YOUTHS

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Abstract

Tobacco and drug abuse is a global concern today with every country having its bit of challenge to confront. This qualitative research was undertaken to assess the culture of alcohol and drug abuse among Ibibio youths of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The study sought to examine how the culture practices influence tobacco abuse among Ibibio youths through traditional marriage and burial ceremonies as practised by the Ibibio people. The researchers made use of Bandura's Social Learning Theory for the theoretical framework. The researchers adopted an exploratory research design. The sample for this study was of age between 18 years and above, who were randomly selected through Fettermen's big-net approach from the selected villages across the Ibibio speaking local government areas in the 3 senatorial districts of Akwa Ibom State. The instrument for data collection was the interview guide. Data were collected through in-depth interviews, key informant interviews, and participant observations. The findings of the study revealed that Ibibio youths take to tobacco abuse as a cultural practice approved by the elders as part of traditional requirements for traditional marriage and burial rites. Among others, the researchers recommends legislative approach toward removal of tobacco products like cigarette and snuff as part of youth items in their traditional requirements for cultural practices.

Keywords: Cultural Practices, Tobacco, Abuse, and Ibibio

Introduction

Tobacco products have been visible and regular items among traditional requirements for cultural activities among the Ibibio people of Akwa Ibom State in southern Nigeria. Tobacco products which include cigarettes, ground snuff, and raw tobacco leaves have been present and treated as key items among required traditional items for cultural practices like

traditional marriage rites, burial rites, the coronation of chiefs and traditional titles.

Culture has been explained from many perspectives about human behaviour and capabilities to adapt to inhabited environments (Peters, 2019). Tylor (1871), as cited in Modo (2016), defined culture as that complex whole that includes knowledge, belief, art, morals, law, customs, and any other capabilities and habits acquired by man as a member of society. Culture explains that members learn the human behaviour of society as part of adaptation's responsibility. Adolescents and youth from the age group whereby humans tend to acquire more human behaviours as part of their transition from childhood to adulthood to adapt to a given environment (Peters, 2019). Culture determines to a large extent what constitutes acceptable foods and drinks in many societies, and the use of any substance in many societies is socially accepted or rejected depending on the sociocultural values and norms of the people (Nwagu *et al.*, 2017; Peters *et al.*, 2023).

Many youths in Nigerian society learned drug abuse as part of adaptability to gangs, and peer groups and as a form of acceptability in the social group (Peters *et al.*, 2023; Peters and Bassey, 2020). Social influence associated with different drug use patterns may be largely responsible for determining individual behaviours and attitudes by shaping the flow of resources to individuals, providing them access to opportunities and placing constraints on behaviour (Jorge *et al.*, 2018).

A drug is a substance that could change biological function through its chemical actions (Okoye, 2001; Peters *et al.*, 2024). The drug is also considered by Balogun (2005) as a substance that modifies perceptions, cognitive, mood behaviour and general body functions. Drug abuse, also called substance abuse or chemical abuse, is a disorder that is characterized by a destructive pattern of using a substance that leads to significant problems or distress (Yusuf *et al.*, 2017). Chronic use of substances can cause serious and sometimes irreversible damage to adolescent's physical and psychological development (Sambo, 2013; Peters *et al.*, 2023). Drug misuse is a term used commonly when the prescription of medication with sedative, anxiolytic, analgesic, or stimulant properties is used for mood alteration or intoxication ignoring the fact that an overdose of such medicines has serious adverse effects (Igiri *et al.*, 2017).

Drug abuse has been on the rise among youths in Nigeria despite the known risk factors and efforts by diverse social, governmental and non-governmental institutions to reduce the pace at which this problem grows within Nigerian society (Ben *et al.*, 2023). The menace of drug abuse in Nigeria has reached a frightening proportion and it pervaded every fibre of society (Yusuf *et al.*, 2017). Drug abuse and its consequences are recognized today as a rapidly growing global social problem (Lakhanpal and Agnihotri, 2007; United Nations Office of Drugs and Crime, 2007).

Cigarettes and other tobacco products like ground snuff abuse, have been on the increase among the youths across the southern region of Nigeria. With its dangerous health implications surrounding tobacco consumption and abuse, this study sought to examine the role of cultural activities in tobacco abuse among youths among the Ibibio people of Akwa Ibom State in Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Nigeria has grown from a drug-consuming to a drug-producing nation (Weekly Trust, 2016), and the rich cultural diversity of Nigeria is practised with the acceptability of some illicit substances making the state of drug use and drug abuse a case of concern today. Culture

and drug abuse have been synonymous from pre-colonial Nigeria. According to Chia *et al.* (2016), psychoactive drugs are used for different reasons, including traditional rites and observances, religious ceremonies, treatment of ailments or palliatives, pleasurable effects, the urge to find acceptance in a particular group, relaxation or stress relief, to forget one's problems, satisfy curiosity and so on. The different cultural setting has their culturally accepted drinks and foods as part of the elements of their society Esen and Peters, 2023; Usoro *et al.*, 2023). Some cultural activities have some specified accepted drinks and foods as traditional items or requirements. Some of these drinks and foods are produced with illicit substances and herbs that can intoxicate.

Abbott and Chase (2008) argued that socio-cultural beliefs can shape the approach to and behaviour regarding substance use and abuse. According to Heath (2001), culture plays a central role in forming the expectations of individuals about potential problems they may face with drug use. The use of drugs by many social groups may be a form of protection factor, such as the use of tobacco by the ancient Aztecs before any contact with white settlers (Abbott and Chase, 2008). The use of Tobacco by the Aztecs was heavily regulated and was only for ceremonial purposes, while non-ceremonial use of tobacco was strictly forbidden under penalty of death (Peters, 2019). Initiation into excessive substance use may occur during periods of rapid social change, often among cultural groups who have had little exposure to a drug and have not developed protective normative behaviour (Abbott and Chase, 2008).

In some parts of Nigeria, the absence of some of these traditional items means an inability to convene or satisfy the people, provoking the wrath of traditions of the people. As part of traditions, some parts of Nigeria have cultural displays in which the bearers cannot or are not allowed to carry such masquerades without being intoxicated with some amount of illicit substances for extraordinary strength to bear the masquerade throughout the stipulated period of cultural display or outing (Peters, 2019; Peters *et al.*, 2023; Usoro *et al.*, 2023). Some parts of the nation have some of these illicit substances as traditional requirements for giving out their children in marriage, coronation of chiefs, selling of portions of lands, burials, annual traditional celebrations of their ancestors, and many other traditional ceremonies.

Youths comprise the largest portion of the Nigerian population both in urban centres and rural Areas (NPC, 2006). The National Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA) (1997) stated that the use and misuse of drugs by adolescents has become one of the most disturbing health-related events in Nigeria especially, among students. The majority of the traditional and cultural activities are carried out or performed by the youths under the supervision, command and authority of the elders. This opportunity created by culture and traditions is often seized by some of these youths to abuse the use of illicit substances hence, the many cases of drug abuse. Cultural values can shape people's attitudes toward substance use and influence their risk of experimentation with drugs (Unger *et al.*, 2004). In Akwa Ibom State, traditions and cultural activities within the society have offered the youths opportunities to produce, demand for, sell, use and abuse illicit substances. The high rate of drug abuse under the disguise of carrying out traditions and cultural activities is disturbing, as the majority of the youths are dependent on drugs and illicit substance consumption. Literature like Chia *et al.* (2016), has presented the use of psychoactive substances for different reasons including traditional rites and observations, religious ceremonies, treatment of ailments or palliatives, but the abuse of these psychoactive drugs as part of

traditional rites and observations, and religious ceremonies by the youths has not been given attention by previous authors which is the main focus of this study. Against this backdrop, this study sought to examine the roles of cultural practices in enhancing tobacco abuse among the young Ibibio people of Akwa Ibom State.

Objectives of the study

The specific objectives of the study were to;

1. The role of traditional marriage ceremony in enhancing tobacco consumption among Ibibio youths in Akwa Ibom State
2. The role of burial rites in enhancing tobacco consumption among Ibibio youths in Akwa Ibom State

Literature Review

Nigerian culture and substance abuse

According to Otile (1990), the culture of Nigeria is shaped by Nigeria's multiple ethnic groups, and the country has 372 languages, seven of which are extinct. Nigeria has major ethnic groups and minor ones. The major ones are considered to be Hausa-Fulani, Yoruba and Igbo. Nigeria's other ethnic groups, sometimes called 'minorities', and are found throughout the country but especially in the north and the middle belt. The traditionally nomadic Fulani can be found all over West and Central Africa. The Fulani and the Hausa are predominantly Muslim while the Igbo are predominantly Christian and so are the Efik, Ibibio, and Annang people. The Yoruba are equally likely to be either Christian or Muslim. Indigenous religious practices remain important to all of Nigeria's ethnic groups, and frequently these beliefs are blended with Christian beliefs, a practice known as syncretism. According to Oluwabamide (2003), Nigeria is a plural country with different cultural groupings which include; Hausa-Fulani, Nok, Igbo ukwu, Ife, Nupe, Yako, Tiv, Yoruba and Benin.

Substance and tobacco use and abuse are rooted in the culture of the people of Nigeria (Peters, 2019). According to Mamman *et al.* (2014), while tobacco and other substances are celebrated in the south, the Northern part of the nation forbids tobacco but accepts cigarettes, kola nut, bitter kola and others. Many ethnic groups in Nigeria culturally accept the use of some substances and tobacco for various purposes. Oluwabamide (2003) posits that different cultural groupings in Nigeria have different ways of practising traditional healthcare services. These traditional healings include the use of herbs, the bark of trees, animals' parts and roots (Oluwabamide, 2003). Much of these substances are mixed with tobacco which serves as an extractive chemical with the capacity to extract from the herbs, the bark of trees, animals' parts and roots the content which will then serve as a drug for treatment. In the course of taking these treatments, many people have developed or cultivated substance and tobacco use and abuse behaviour. Traditional healthcare providers and their practices are culturally accepted by the Nigerian society. In some parts of the cultural Areas where tobacco is not religiously accepted, some people take tobacco as medicine for the treatment of some illnesses through the patronage of traditional health caregivers.

Dumbili (2013) argued that in Nigeria, tobacco consumption has a long history, particularly among groups where it was not forbidden by religion. It is consumed greatly during rituals, marriage ceremonies, burials and funerals. During such occasions, palm wine and hot drinks are specifically used in pouring libations, offering prayers and heralding such

events. Among the most commonly consumed tobacco beverages are; palm wine–fermented from the sap of oil palm tree, beer, *burukutu*–fermented from guinea-corn and native gin–distilled from palm wine (Wilson *et al.*, 2023). Nigerian in 2010 had a total tobacco per capita (15+) consumption of 23.1 litres of pure tobacco among male and female drinkers. This did not include the large quantity of homemade tobacco consumed which usually goes unrecorded (Nwagu *et al.*, 2017).

While low to moderate consumption of tobacco products may not cause any harm to the drinker, heavy and uncontrolled consumption, especially among young people predispose drinkers to numerous health challenges (WHO, 2014). Drinking in any community can, however, be influenced by the social and cultural norms of the community. If community members are properly guided, they can play useful roles in controlling tobacco abuse, hence preventing tobacco problems, particularly among young people (Nwagu *et al.*, 2017).

Many developing countries are highly dependent on national revenues from tobacco. Individuals in many rural communities in such countries also depend on income from tobacco products such as cigarettes and stuff, however, worth noting that when the production of such homemade tobacco products increases in a bid to increase income by producers, consumption also increases (Ben *et al.*, 2023). Palm wine produced in many rural communities is a perishable commodity which needs to be consumed or it spoils. Members of Enugu Ezike produce and consume palm wine in large quantities. Some researchers have noted that in many developing countries, tobacco is often more readily available than clean drinking water. This seems to be the case in Enugu Ezike where this study was conducted (Nwagu *et al.*, 2017).

Traditional marriages and substance/tobacco use and abuse

Oluwatoyin and Afolabi (2013) argued that traditional marriage festival is a tourism potential that is yet to be fully recognized by the people and government. They maintained that for every culture there is usually something unique and spectacular about the way the marriage is being conducted which attracts the tourist attention. They further posit that traditional marriage is usually accompanied by a lot of merriment and enjoyment. These merriment and enjoyment is always associated with use and in some cases abuse of substance which are often collected as part of traditional marriage requirement. The items collected as traditional marriage requirements are relative to ethnic group or cultural setting. While tobacco drink is religiously forbidden among the Hausa and Fulani of the northern Nigeria, it is a major item among most of the southern ethnic groups in Nigerians. The forbidden of tobacco products by the Hausa and Fulani automatically compel the exclusion of such items in traditional marriage requirement among these ethnic groups. Items like Kola nuts are culturally and religiously accepted by these ethnic groups, and this makes Kola nut part of their traditional marriage requirements.

Oluwatoyin and Afolabi (2013) said that traditional wedding could be coined to be the art of joining a man and a woman of age who have agreed to live together with the express consent of the parents of both parties in line with the norms and customs of the people in question. Oluwatoyin and Afolabi's (2013) research in Ekiti state, shows that of the 195 respondents that are aware of Traditional marriage, 48.7% classify it as Traditional/Cultural, this means that the respondents see it as festival that could project the cultural heritage of the people; 40.5% classify it as Tourism potential, meaning that the members of the community

should be educated and be informed that the Traditional marriage Ceremony has tourism potentials. Part of the beauties of the Traditional marriage in some parts of Nigeria is the presence of tobacco and other substances.

According to Nzoiwu (2012), marriage in Igbo land or any other African country goes beyond procreation or marital relationship. Traditionally, Igbo marriage institutions are marked by extensive prohibitions on unions between close relatives and the use of marriage obligation to interlink basic social groups within numerous and widely scattered communities. Women are also forbidden to marry within their own patrilineal lineage or those of their mother and their father's mother. This regulation eliminates not only parallel cousin marriage but also rules out cross cousins. As such, basic lineages groups do not become placed into paired or circular exchange system as they do in many other societies with basic unilateral descent structures similar to the Igbo. At times, a child develops special relationships with his mother and father mother's patrilineal lineage. People must marry outside of their community of origin, since all of its inhabitants usually belong to a common patrilineal group. According to Basden (1912) cited in Nzoiwu (2012), in those cases where separate lineage occupy the same village or someone is born and raised in a foreign settlement, the local exogamy restriction still applies.

Brown (1975) cited in Nzoiwu (2012) asserts that: No marriage was recognized as valid without fulfilling the customary conditions. Living together as “husband and wife” without performing the traditional marriage rites is not a recognized union. Especially in traditional settings in Nigeria, before any marriage or union between a man and a woman as “husband and wife” can be recognised as legal union and accorded the deserved respect, traditional marriage rites must be performed by the parties involved in accordance with the cultural demands of the people involved. According to Nzoiwu (2012), traditional marriage rite is defined as the ceremonies surrounding marriage within a traditional setting according to the customary laws and tradition of the people involved. It involves series of negotiations, presentation of gift, payments and in some cases divination. Traditional marriage rite process can take years from when the girl is betrothed from childhood to when she is actually established in her husband's house (Peters, 2024).

Burial rites and substance use and Abuse

According to Story (2016), in a small village in Togo, Sub-Saharan Africa, it takes few weeks or months after the dead body has been buried in a round egg-like hole to commence the burial ceremony which takes a different pattern from what is obtainable in other parts of Africa. According to her, it is always recommended to conduct funeral ceremony after the farming season so that the villagers can have time to attend to dance and smoke their locally produced tobacco product. According to Karen Story's report of her eye witness account of burial rites in Togo, she narrated the death and burial of an old woman in a small village in Togo. The old woman lived in a small mud hut. The round, thatch-roofed dwelling was perched on a terrace below some cliffs, with a sweeping view of a boulder-strewn slope, and a valley below. The old woman lay on her sleeping mat in the small, round room. A granary in the center kept the harvest safe from thieves and animals. The old woman was curled on her side, covered with a cloth, facing the wall. Groups of old men were installed in quiet clusters in the shade. One couldn't help wondering if they were dwelling more than usual on their own impending mortality. The body had been moved to a mattress on a metal bed frame. Around it was a cluster of wailing women. The faint sound of drums

and wailing women echoed across the valley (Story, 2016).

The story further explained that once the old woman was positioned, two young men with short-handled hoes stepped forward and began scooping in the dirt. As the hole filled, they tamped the dirt with sticks and rocks. Some quarrelling began among the old men, and the crowd started to drift away. One of the old woman's twenty-something granddaughters stood next to me, wide-eyed, and gasped, "My god, they're jumping up and down on my grandma!" The story went back to the funeral house and drank some millet beer under a crescent moon and a sky full of stars before heading home and leaving the crowd to its all-night vigil. After three days the family elders would meet to decide how and when the funeral ceremonies would take place.

According to Story (2016), in a farming economy, it makes sense to wait until the off-season to hold the funeral, when people have more time. Grandma's funeral was held months later. The family fed multitudes. There was all-night dancing to the beat of two-tone flutes and "talking" drums. The dancers shuffled in a circle for hours, sustained by kola nuts and millet beer, falling into a kind of trance. The next morning they returned to their homes, joyful, and radiant, as if huge weights had been lifted from their shoulders. And perhaps they had. In this burial ceremony among the Togolese, tobacco use and abuse is present according to Karen Story's report. The locally made millet beer which is also found among the Sango-Kataff people of Northern Nigeria is locally called "Brukutu". This locally made beer has been culturally acceptable and has provided the basis for tobacco consumption among the people of Togo and Nigeria.

Theoretical Framework

Social Learning Theory

Social learning theory is a framework that explains the learning process and social behaviour, suggesting that individuals can acquire new behaviours by observing and imitating others (Miller, 2011). This theory posits that learning is a cognitive activity that occurs within a social environment and can happen solely through observation or direct teaching, even without the need for physical reproduction or immediate reinforcement (Bandura, 2004). Beyond merely observing actions, individuals also learn by witnessing the consequences of those actions, a phenomenon referred to as vicarious reinforcement. When a specific behaviour is consistently rewarded, it is likely to continue; on the other hand, if a behaviour is frequently punished, it is likely to cease (Bandura, 1971). This theory builds upon traditional behavioural models, which focus exclusively on reinforcements, by highlighting the significant influence of various internal cognitive processes on the learner (Bandura, 1963).

In this framework, Albert Bandura examined learning processes that transpired in interpersonal settings, which were insufficiently addressed by operant conditioning theories or prevailing social learning models (Bandura, 1971). Bandura specifically contended that "the shortcomings of learning approaches that overlook the impact of social variables are most evident in their treatment of the acquisition of novel responses" (Bandura, 1963). Skinner's explanation for the acquisition of new responses was based on the principle of successive approximation, necessitating numerous trials, reinforcement of behavioural components, and gradual modification (Renzetti *et al.*, 2012). Rotter's theory suggested that the probability of a behaviour occurring is influenced by the subjective expectancy and value of the reinforcement (Chomsky, 1995). This model presupposed a hierarchy of pre-existing

responses and, as Bandura noted in 2004, failed to consider responses that had not yet been learned. Consequently, Bandura initiated research on the swift acquisition of new behaviours through social observation, with the Bobo doll experiments being the most notable. Social Learning Theory merges behavioural and cognitive learning theories to create a holistic model capable of explaining the diverse range of learning experiences encountered in real life. As initially outlined by Bandura and Walters in 1963 and further detailed in 1977 (Grusec, 1992), the key tenets of Social Learning Theory are as follows:

- i. Learning is not purely behavioural; rather, it is a cognitive process that takes place in a social context.
- ii. Learning can occur by observing a behaviour and by observing the consequences of the behaviour (vicarious reinforcement).
- iii. Learning involves observation, extraction of information from those observations, and making decisions about the performance of the behaviour (observational learning or modelling). Thus, learning can occur without an observable change in behaviour.
- iv. Reinforcement plays a role in learning but is not entirely responsible for learning.
- v. The learner is not a passive recipient of information. Cognition, environment, and behaviour all mutually influence each other (reciprocal determinism).

Methodology

This research employed an ethnographic design to observe and collect data regarding the influence of cultural activities on tobacco use and abuse among the Ibibio youth in Akwa Ibom State. This approach is particularly effective for exploring, investigating, and explaining significant issues related to the study, thereby providing valuable insights for future research on the various variables identified by the researcher. The study was carried out in Ibibio-speaking local government areas across each of the three senatorial districts of Akwa Ibom State. A community was randomly selected from each of the chosen local government areas: Ibiono, Onna, and Ibesikpo Asutan. The big-net sampling technique was utilized to draw participants from the field.

For data collection, the researchers employed an interview schedule consisting of open-ended questions, enabling respondents to provide information freely without being constrained to specific answers (Esen and Peters, 2023; Esen and Peters, 2023). All questions were translated into the Ibibio language during the interviews. The data gathered were analyzed thematically, using verbatim excerpts with pseudonyms to present the findings of the study.

Result

Traditional Marriage Ceremonies and Drug Abuse

Emerging from observations, interviews, and discussions regarding the use of traditional marriage ceremonies by youths as a platform for drug abuse is the significant cultural influence of the Ibibio people, particularly in the Ibibio-speaking Local Government Areas. This cultural context includes a traditional requirement list that effectively serves as a moral justification for the consumption of substances, including tobacco, leading to their misuse among the youth. The researcher found that it is customary for the Ibibio community to include various types and brands of tobacco drinks, along with other psychoactive

substances, as part of the requirements for marrying off their daughters. Family heads, who participated as key informants in the study, indicated that this practice has been established by their ancestors and is considered a longstanding tradition. Consequently, they feel unable to alter a practice that has been accepted by the community for generations.

According to one of the study participants aged 49 years:

I know that our tradition is strong and somehow very practical, it has been here with us, we inherited it from our fathers who inherited it from their fathers; that tobacco items like snuff, cigarette and those other items whether it is intoxicated or psychoactive substances must be collected as part of traditional marriage requirements for giving out our daughters. That is why we do stress the point Traditional Marriage Requirements so that one will know that it a tradition, It is in inherited and transmitted from one generation to another (Udy, Generator repairer, 49, interviewed 12/2/2025).

Participants emphasized the role of list content of traditional marriage requirement as key cultural provisions for tobacco and psychoactive substance abuse among the youths in Ibibio speaking Local Government Areas. They agreed that there are such items like illicit gin, schnapps, different brands of hot drink, tobacco leaves, grinded snuff, beer of different brands, palm wine, and petrol cannot be excluded from the traditional marriage requirement list for any reasons what so ever.

One of the male study participants aged 53 years explained:

You cannot take some items out of our marriage requirement list. If you do, then it is no longer traditional marriage, in fact it will be as if you are rating your daughter with a fowl. Those items like illicit gin, palm wine, tobacco, snuff, hot drinks, and beer, are what make the marital requirement list traditional and celebrative. This is because, everything other items like the cloths and bride price belong to the parents, but these other items are what the parents do share with the people and youths also have their own share. Therefore, if the youths abuse it, that is their own cup of tea, but tradition is tradition (Nne 53, interviewed 4/2/2025).

As part of observation and interview, the youths are given a special section of the traditional marriage requirement with items that are capable of intoxicating them. It was gathered by the researcher that there is a part of the traditional marriage requirement list which is referred to as "Youths' Items". This section of the list contains items like cigarettes (tobacco) of different brands, ground snuff (tobacco), kola nut, illicit gin, hot drinks, beer, palm wine, and other items. The youths have over the years and generations, collected such items as part of their requirement for giving out one of their own in marriage.

Burial Ceremonies and Drug Abuse

The examination of burial rites and drug abuse among the Ibibio people highlights various elements of their funeral ceremonies. These elements include "ubob ndak," which pertains to the construction of a traditional tent; and "ukpok ndak," the dismantling and

dispersal of the traditional tent.

According to information gathered through interviews, these sub-cultural components of the Ibibio burial rites reveal cultural practices that encourage the consumption of tobacco and other psychoactive substances. Participants in the study indicated that illicit gin, palm wine, beer, tobacco, and other alcoholic beverages are procured through an assessment list provided by in-laws and relatives. In some instances, these items are purchased for the bereaved family using funds collected from immediate relatives or family members.

One participant, aged 40, shared insights into how tobacco and psychoactive substances are gathered and distributed among attendees during burial ceremonies. According to him:

In our community we collect illicit gin, palm wine, hot drinks and other food items from our in-laws and other relatives through what we call assessment. These items are used for entertainment during the burial rites. These items are consumed by our people according to the cultural grouping of people during the burial ceremonies. The youths (iwaad) are always given their special place and entertained with items like beer, illicit gin, hot drink, palm wine, and food items. This is tradition which is carried out all over Ibibio is customized to be right by our forefathers, and there is nothing wrong with it (Eke 40, interviewed 7/2/2025).

A 36-year-old participant in the study shared in his accounts that due to the cultural acceptance of psychoactive substance use, young individuals often bring items such as cigarettes, marijuana, ground snuff (tobacco), and various psychoactive concoctions to traditional ceremonies, including funerals.

According to his words, he said:

You cannot take tobacco out of youth's items for any reason. It is something that the elders have authorized and there is nothing you can do. So we the youths just go ahead and taker what our fathers have accepted for us and there is no evil in it because it is what the elders have prescribed for the youths (Ekpai 36 interviewed 7/2/2025).

In the Ibibio-speaking regions of Ibibio land, burial ceremonies involve a variety of traditional rites, as noted by study participants. One such rite is known as "ubub ndak," which refers to the construction of a traditional tent. Based on observations and discussions, this specific rite is typically conducted one or two days prior to the burial ceremony. It has been noted that this occasion often provides a chance for young individuals to engage in the misuse of tobacco and other psychoactive substances.

Discussion of Findings

The study reveals that cultural practices, such as traditional marriage and burial ceremonies, provide opportunities for the abuse of psychoactive substances among the Ibibio youth in the Ibibio-speaking Local Government Areas. The research indicates that the list of requirements for traditional marriage holds significant importance within these

ceremonies among the Ibibio community. Additionally, the researcher found that the traditional marriage list includes tobacco and other psychoactive substances, such as tobacco snuff, cigarettes, and penetrol, prevalent among the Ibibio people in Akwa Ibom State. Local cultural norms play a crucial role in influencing tobacco use (Peters, 2019).

It was observed that the collection of psychoactive substances as part of the traditional marriage customs for giving daughters in marriage is viewed as a practice established by their ancestors and has been preserved through generations. According to Peters et al. (2024), tobacco and other substances are celebrated in southern Nigeria. Further research indicates that the youth perceive the cultural acceptance of these psychoactive substances by their fathers as a moral justification for consuming tobacco, smoking cigarettes, using marijuana, inhaling tobacco in the form of snuff, and producing these substances. The most commonly consumed tobacco beverages include palm wine, which is fermented from the sap of the oil palm tree, beer, burukutu, which is fermented from guinea corn, and native gin, distilled from palm wine (Wilson *et al.*, 2023).

The study's findings indicate that the Ibibio clan, residing in Ibibio-speaking Local Government Areas, incorporates burial rites that involve the use of tobacco and psychoactive substances. The research highlights the significant role of the youth, in these burial ceremonies, noting their influence on the items designated as youths' items. These items, as revealed by the findings, include tobacco and other psychoactive substances, which are traditionally accepted and customarily presented to the youth during various burial rites, such as “ubub ndak” (the construction of the traditional tent), “ukpok ndak” (the dismantling of the conventional tent), and on the day of the burial itself. The consumption of tobacco-based beverages has been a vital component of numerous cultures for millennia (McGovern, 2009).

Conclusion

The primary aim of this research was to investigate how cultural practices contribute to tobacco use among young people in the Ibibio-speaking Local Government Areas of Akwa Ibom State. Cultural events such as traditional marriages and burial ceremonies often incorporate tobacco and other psychoactive substances. Consequently, Ibibio youth frequently engage in tobacco use through cigarettes and snuff, viewing it as a customary aspect of these cultural practices. Young individuals play a crucial role in society, and within the Ibibio-speaking Local Government Areas, they take advantage of opportunities presented by tradition to consume and misuse psychoactive substances. This behaviour is often justified by the belief that such substances are integral to the cultural rituals endorsed by their elders.

Recommendations

- The following recommendations are made from the findings of this research:
- i. Tobacco substances like cigarettes and snuff should be removed from traditional requirement lists for cultural events for youths.
 - ii. Community elders should not encourage the collection of tobacco and psychoactive substances for youths as part of tradition.

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